

Technical Note on Argumentation in Ransomware Negotiation

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Abstract

Ransomware extortion is both a technical attack and a negotiation in which attackers seek payment and victims try to limit loss, gain time, and test the threat’s credibility. In this paper, we study publicly leaked ransomware negotiations as argumentative dialogues and analyse them through dialogue types, dialogue moves, and argumentation schemes. We leverage a two-stage, adjudicated annotation workflow for hostile conversational data, where inferential episodes often span several short messages and do not align with message boundaries. The analysis shows that ransomware negotiation is not mere coercion: negotiation dialogue and practical reasoning dominate, while value appeals, causal forecasts, evidential claims, and procedural manoeuvres also shape the exchange. Hence, ransomware negotiation can be effectively analysed with computational argumentation and such analysis requires methods designed for compressed, strategic, and coercive dialogue.

Keywords: Ransomware negotiation; Argumentation schemes; Dialogical annotation

1 Introduction

Ransomware extortion (see Figure 1 for an example) begins as a technical intrusion and then becomes a negotiation process. Contemporary ransomware operations work within a mature criminal market in which different units of a criminal organisation often handle access, deployment, payment processing, and victim

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management as specialised roles and services [27]. Major groups run extortion as an organised business process, not as a purely opportunistic act [14]. Negotiation is thus one of the mechanisms by which attackers turn disruptive access into revenue, and one of the mechanisms by which victims try to test whether the threat is credible, reduce financial loss, or buy time [4, 30].

Existing research (Section 2) has clarified the economics of ransomware, the legal and operational dilemmas of engagement, and the broad structure of bargaining under uncertainty [27, 4, 30]. What remains unclear is whether ransomware negotiations contain a genuine argumentative component at all, rather than merely threats, scripts, and price haggling. If they do, the next questions are whether their dominant logic is coercive or practical, whether particular ransomware groups display distinct argumentative signatures, and what role value-based appeals play in shaping bargaining and discounts.

We study ransomware negotiation as argumentative dialogue: in Walton’s dialogue theory, arguments are moves within dialogue types oriented to different goals and conversational contexts [33]. Commitment-based dialogue models further clarify the burdens and obligations that attach to such exchanges [35]. Hence, negotiation is more than a sequence of offers and counteroffers: it is a dialogue in which the parties advance and contest reasons under severe asymmetries of power, information, and stakes. Building on top of our earlier investigation [7], to analyse those reasons, we use argumentation schemes, understood as stereotypical patterns of defeasible reasoning [34]. Practical reasoning is particularly apt here because the participants repeatedly argue from goals, constraints, and proposed courses of action [22].

The contribution is both methodological and empirical. Methodologically (Section 3), we adopt a boundary-first, two-stage, adjudicated workflow for a hostile conversational setting in which inferential units often spread across several short messages and cannot be recovered reliably from message boundaries alone. This differs from our previous analyses [7, 9] where we looked at simpler speech acts. Empirically (Section 4), we provide a structured annotation of leaked – allegedly real – ransomware negotiation episodes at the level of argument scheme, dialogue type, and dialogue move.

The analysis shows that ransomware negotiation is not reducible to undifferentiated coercion: negotiation dialogue and practical reasoning dominate, while value appeals, causal forecasting, evidential claims, and procedural manoeuvring play smaller but still important roles. Ransomware negotiation can thus be effectively studied through computational models of argumentation, not only through economic, legal, or game-theoretic lenses. Ultimately, extortion is a communicative practice and extends argumentation research into a domain shaped by coercion, strategic opacity, and compressed reasoning.

Figure 1: Condensed timeline of the 2023 SIRVA/BGRS incident. SIRVA and BGRS were major contractors of the Canadian government specialised in employee relocation solutions. Circumstantial evidence links a chat included in this study to this incident (dots in gray in the timeline), but no public source appears to authenticate the leaked transcript itself.²

2 Related Work

Most ransomware research examines the economics, organisation, and operation of the extortion ecosystem. Studies of payment markets describe a mature and specialised environment where intrusion, payment handling, and victim management may be split across actors and services [27]. More recent work reinforces that view by framing ransomware as an organised extortion business and by tracing phases and influence strategies in actual negotiations [14, 23, 10].

A smaller literature addresses negotiation itself. Legal and operational studies clarify the main stages and dilemmas of engagement [4]. Recent technical and exploratory work has begun to inspect the language of ransomware negotiation directly [7]. Formal models treat targeted ransomware negotiation and related double-extortion signaling as strategic interaction [30, 24]. These studies look at strategy, incentives, and decision structure, but not at the specific argumentative tactics used.

The closest methodological work comes from dialogical argument annotation and multilayer corpus design. Prior work proposes models for annotating illocutionary structure and argumentation in debate and tools for dialogue-based argument analysis [6, 17]. This line has been extended with online support for argument-scheme annotation, showing both the promise and the difficulty of reliable scheme labelling at scale [20]. More recent shared-task and corpus work

²Sources: <https://www.canada.ca/en/department-national-defence/maple-leaf/defence/2023/10/update-incident-affecting-brookfield-global-relocation-services-systems.html>; <https://www.canada.ca/en/treasury-board-secretariat/news/2023/11/message-to-current-and-former-public-service-employees-and-members-of-the-canadian-armed-forces-and-royal-canadian-mounted-police.html>; <https://www.bleepingcomputer.com/news/security/canadian-government-discloses-data-breach-after-contractor-hacks/>; (on 1 April 2026).

Figure 2: Excerpt from the chat between allegedly SIRVA/BGSC and members of the *Lockbit3.0* criminal gang: **V** denotes the victim and **A** the attacker. The exchange shows the basic extortion sequence of demand, price announcement, verification request, and proof offer.

has pushed dialogical argument mining itself, including DialAM-2024 and QT-Schemes [29, 28]. Related work also offers multilayer corpora linking schemes to other discourse relations, though in very different genres [25].

From an argument-mining perspective, the closest work lies in research on dialogical corpora and annotation disagreement. Surveys show that existing pipelines still favour monological data and serve dialogical, adversarial, and strategically compressed exchanges less well [19]. Important dialogical corpora do exist, including large-scale resources for political and broadcast debate such as QT30 [15], but they come from public deliberation rather than criminal extortion under asymmetric coercion. Work on disagreement is particularly relevant because it argues that disagreement should be analysed structurally rather than reduced to a single reliability score [16].

3 Methodology

Ransomware chats are adversarial negotiations: see in Figure 2 an excerpt from the Sirva incident discussed in Figure 1. In them, argumentative force is often distributed across short, strategically ordered, mixed-function exchanges, a pattern that is consistent with the communicative and organisational complexity of ransomware extortion [23]. They are not monologues with neatly separable argumentative parts, and they are not mere streams of isolated messages that can be labelled one by one.

The relevant unit of analysis is therefore the locally coherent argumentative

discourse unit (ADU) [6, 5], understood here as a contiguous stretch of dialogue that realises one primary argumentative function within the negotiation, through which one party advances, resists, or reshapes a bargaining position. This choice follows work that anchors arguments in locutions, dialogue acts, and relations between propositions as interaction unfolds, as in Inference Anchoring Theory (IAT) [6, 5, 17, 18]. Under IAT, an ADU is a span of discourse whose propositional content is anchored in a locution or in a transition directed at that locution, and whose content has a discrete argumentative function because it stands in an inferential, conflictive, or reformulative relation to other propositions [6, 5, 17, 18]. In ransomware negotiations, that discourse is highly compressed. A single argumentative move may be distributed across several short messages, while a single message may combine proof, threat, justification, and bargaining.

We study 46 of the 241 chats in the *Ransomchats* dataset,³ those in which the final demand is lower than the initial demand. These 46 chats come from 10 of the 25 ransomware groups represented in the dataset. They are the cases in which one can argue that bargaining has left a measurable trace in the record. We operationalise negotiation outcome as a discount ratio, computed by subtracting the final demand from the opening demand and dividing the result by the opening demand.

We abstract away from timing and from fine-grained linguistic form so that the chats can be represented as structured sequences of ADUs annotated for their argumentative and dialogical properties. This choice leaves aside other important aspects of negotiation, including tempo, delay, abuse, and other local linguistic features. Even so, the choice is forced in part by the data itself: the dataset does not provide complete timestamps for all messages, and a full linguistic or temporal analysis lies beyond the scope of this paper.

The workflow has two stages. The first stage identifies ADUs; the second annotates them. These are distinct tasks. At each stage, two large language models (LLMs) – *Annotatator 1* and *Annotatator 2* – annotate independently, and a third model – *Judge* – adjudicates between them. This reflects a standard problem in argumentation annotation: disagreement is often substantive. In that setting, inter-annotation agreement is informative but incomplete, because unitisation and classification errors are easily conflated [1, ?, 26]. We therefore use the *Judge* as the endpoint of the workflow to produce a single stable and inspectable final annotation for each case. An interested reader can find the complete description of the used prompts in [2]. *Annotatator 1* and *Annotatator 2* are Azure OpenAI gpt-5-mini⁴ and Amazon Bedrock Claude Haiku 4.5. The *Judge* in both stages

³<https://github.com/Casualtek/Ransomchats> commit 1871e48 (1 April 2026).

⁴In three Stage 2 cases, Azure content filtering blocked one annotator, and Claude Sonnet 4.5 was

Table 1: Negotiation phases used in stage-1 boundary annotation

Phase	Operational definition
Contact and identification	The exchange establishes contact, identifies the parties, or orients the interaction.
Proof exchange	The exchange requests or provides proof of compromise, possession, decryptability, or credibility.
Bargaining	The exchange advances settlement-oriented argument, including demands, affordability claims, concessions, and counteroffers.
Payment arrangement	The exchange coordinates the practical conditions of payment, including wallets, transfer instructions, timing, and execution.
Post-payment	The exchange concerns obligations after payment, such as decryptor delivery, deletion claims, troubleshooting, or technical follow-up.
Breakdown or walk-away	The exchange records refusal, impasse, abandonment, or collapse of the negotiation.

is Amazon Bedrock Claude Sonnet 4.5. This separation between first-pass annotation and adjudication reduces the risk that one model’s preferences simply propagate unchecked through the pipeline. Recent work shows that LLMs can perform competitively across a range of computational argumentation tasks [8], and that annotation quality depends strongly on prompt design, explicit class definitions, and guideline conditioning [31, 21, 3]. Adjacent work also shows that appropriate prompting and priming can improve relation-based mining [13].

Stage 1 deals only with boundaries. It marks off ADUs before any inferential labelling begins. Boundary decisions are guided by the macro-structural organisation of the negotiation, using the phase inventory in Table 1. These phases are corpus-sensitive analytical categories designed to capture recurrent transitions in ransomware negotiation. They draw on crisis-negotiation work on phases, influence strategies, and high-stakes interaction [11, 12], and on recent ransomware-specific work that identifies phases and influence strategies in extortion negotiations [10].

Stage 2 annotates each ADU for both inferential form and local interactional function, following [25, 20]. The restricted scheme inventory appears in Table 2, and the dialogue-move inventory in Table 3. This stage answers two distinct questions as a fallback annotator.

Table 2: Argumentation schemes available in the stage-2 annotation inventory

Scheme	Operational definition
Practical reasoning	The ADU supports a course of action by presenting it as a means to achieve a stated or implied goal.
Argument from negative consequences	The ADU supports a conclusion by stressing the harmful consequences of refusal, delay, or non-compliance.
Argument from positive consequences	The ADU supports a conclusion by stressing the beneficial consequences of compliance, cooperation, or timely action.
Argument from sign	The ADU uses an observed sign, indicator, or token as evidence for a further state of affairs, such as possession, capability, or prior action.
Argument from position to know	The ADU relies on the speaker’s claimed access, authority, or knowledge as grounds for what should be believed.
Argument from commitment	The ADU appeals to a prior statement, promise, concession, or undertaking as a reason for what should follow.
Argument from values	The ADU justifies or criticises a course of action by reference to values, priorities, or normative commitments.
No clear scheme	The ADU is argumentative, but no single scheme in the restricted inventory provides a sufficiently defensible fit.

tions: what kind of argument scheme a given ADU instantiates, and what that ADU is doing at that point in the negotiation. The resulting representation captures both the argumentative logic of the ADU – for example, Practical reasoning or Argument from negative consequences in the Walton–Reed–Macagno tradition of argumentation schemes [34] – and its situated role in the dialogue, such as Counteroffer, Threaten, or Payment execution.

Dialogue moves in Table 3 are informed by Walton’s dialogue theory, especially the distinction between negotiation and adjacent modes such as persuasion, information-seeking, and eristic exchange [35]. Ransomware chats are hybrid dialogues in which bargaining, burden management, information exchange, and strategic justification coexist. This is coherent with seeing negotiations as dialogues in which argumentative exchanges remain structurally central [32]. ADUs that in-

Figure 3: Agreement scores for both stages cluster around the low-to-high 80s.

stantiate similar schemes may still play different roles in the unfolding negotiation: opening, demand, counteroffer, rejection, proof, commitment, concession, payment execution, or delivery. Dialogue-move annotation therefore complements the scheme layer by making it possible to reconstruct negotiation sequences rather than merely count decontextualised argumentative types.

4 Results

The results show a reliable annotation pipeline, a clear dominance of practical over coercive reasoning, distinct argumentative profiles across groups, and a special role for value appeals when they are turned into bargaining moves. The analysis below develops those findings in turn, from validation to scheme dominance to value appeals. The results come from a Bayesian analysis with maximum-entropy priors conditional on the relevant support constraints.⁵

4.1 Validating the annotation pipeline

For both stages of the pipeline, Figure 3 shows high agreement between *Annotator 1* and *Annotator 2*.⁶ Under this model, the agreement between the two

⁵For proportion parameters, we use Beta(1, 1) priors; for Bayesian bootstrap estimands, we use the standard Dirichlet(1, ..., 1) prior over weights.

⁶Agreement is assessed by the *Judge*, which compares the two independent annotations against the source transcript and returns both an overall agreement score and dimension-specific scores; the subsequent Bayesian analysis treats these judge-assigned per-chat scores as the observed agreement

annotators at Stage 1 (*i.e.*, ADUs’ boundary identification) has a posterior mean of 82.86, with a 95 % credible interval (CrI) of [81.49, 84.12]. The agreement at Stage 2 (*i.e.*, scheme and dialogue identification) has a posterior mean of 83.94, with a 95 % CrI of [82.57, 85.15]. Both sit comfortably above the 80-point high-agreement floor, so the corpus-level result is not driven by a few unusually easy cases.

Stage 1 shows higher disagreement on boundaries than on substance. Annotators agree more strongly about inferential content than about exact segmentation. Inferential-core alignment exceeds span alignment by 4.76 points (95 % CrI [3.75, 5.74]) and reply-structure alignment by 7.26 points (95 % CrI [6.12, 8.73]). Stage 2 shows higher disagreement on scheme labels than on the underlying content. Claim-premise alignment exceeds scheme alignment by 9.53 points (95 % CrI [7.61, 11.32]), dialogue-move alignment by 7.00 points (95 % CrI [5.11, 8.92]), and dialogue-type alignment by 13.47 points (95 % CrI [10.52, 16.23]). In short, the pipeline first stabilizes ADUs and then asks the harder question of which argumentative function each unit instantiates.

4.2 Dominant schemes and group-level signatures

Practical reasoning is the dominant argumentative pattern in ransomware negotiations. It appears more often than coercive reasoning and is driven more by bargaining, feasibility claims, and settlement-oriented reasoning than by naked threats, especially during bargaining and payment-arrangement exchanges. Practical reasoning occurs 224 times, whereas Argument from negative consequences occurs 129 times. The posterior mean share of Practical reasoning is 0.634, with a 95 % CrI of [0.583, 0.683]. On the practical-versus-coercive contrast, about two thirds of the expected mass therefore falls on practical reasoning.

That dominance holds at chat level as well. The posterior mean share of chats in which Practical reasoning outnumbers Argument from negative consequences is 0.690 (95 % CrI [0.545, 0.819]), with posterior probability 0.995 that a majority of decisive chats are dominated by arguments from practical reasoning. The average chat-level margin between practical-reasoning and negative-consequence share is 0.150 (95 % CrI [0.077, 0.223]). The dominance of arguments for practical reasoning is therefore not a trace effect or an artifact of a few large chats; it recurs across the corpus.

Groups also display distinct argumentative profiles. As Figure 4 shows, groups differ in both scheme use and bargaining behaviour. The figure combines scheme-level indicators with move-level markers such as *provide proof*, *counteroffer*, and

data. See [2] for details.

Figure 4: Criminal groups exhibit distinct argumentative signatures, as shown by heatmap of group-level mean argumentative features, including scheme use (Practical reasoning, Argument from negative consequences, Argument from commitment; see Table 2), dialogue moves (Provide proof, Counteroffer, Threaten; see Table 3), and two sequence markers for the Demand or anchor → Counteroffer → Accept/Payment execution/Delivery or fulfilment pattern and the proof-before-bargaining pattern.

threaten, and adds two binary sequence features that capture recurrent ordering patterns rather than frequency. Across groups with at least 3 chats, the posterior mean range in practical-versus-negative balance is 0.289 (95 % CrI [0.111, 0.499]), with posterior probability 0.984 that the range exceeds 0.10. Scheme-level proof orientation also varies across groups, with posterior mean range 0.128 and posterior probability 0.931 that the range exceeds 0.08. Threat intensity varies more weakly, with posterior mean range 0.091 and posterior probability 0.897 that the range exceeds 0.05.

Pairwise contrasts make those group signatures concrete. For instance, the negotiators associated with *Conti* are more proof-heavy than those associated with *Akira*, with posterior mean difference 0.076 and posterior probability 0.991 that the difference is positive. Thus, group style varies in a way that is visible beyond the aggregate averages.

Figure 5: Value appeals have only a weak direct association with larger discounts, but the pattern is stronger when they lead immediately into a counteroffer.

4.3 Value appeals as bargaining pivots

Value appeals are rare and their direct association with larger discounts is weak. They appear in only 22 instances across 14 of the 46 discounted chats. Chats containing at least one value appeal show a posterior mean discount advantage of 10.2 percentage points relative to chats without value appeals, but the uncertainty is large (95 % CrI $[-5.7, 26.3]$ percentage points). The direct effect is therefore suggestive rather than decisive.

The more interesting pattern is sequential. Figure 5 shows that chats containing at least one immediate transition from Argument from values to a Counteroffer have a higher posterior mean discount percentage than value-appeal chats without such a transition. The posterior mean difference is 16.3 percentage points, and the posterior probability that the effect is positive is 0.942, although the interval still overlaps zero (95 % CrI $[-3.5, 39.7]$ percentage points). Most posterior mass therefore favours a positive bargaining-pivot effect, even though the estimate remains uncertain.

As Figure 5 shows, value appeals usually feed back into bargaining rather than ending it. The dialogue move annotations point in the same direction: the posterior mean share of value appeals labelled as Bargaining is 0.833, so most value appeals function inside bargaining rather than outside it. When a value appeal is followed by another argumentative unit, the posterior mean probability that the dialogue returns immediately to negotiation is 0.957. Among direct bargaining *vs.* escalation successors, the posterior mean Counteroffer share is 0.769, with posterior probability 0.981 that counteroffers outnumber Threaten moves. Value appeals are

Figure 6: Both victims and attackers use Argument from values annotations, but they attach them to different local moves. The heatmap shows within-role shares in the range $[0, 1]$, with y-axis labels reporting the total number of Argument from values annotations for each speaker role.

therefore not dead-end moral gestures. In this corpus, they usually feed back into bargaining.

Victims and attackers both use value appeals, but they do so in different local move contexts. As Figure 6 shows, victims use them more often overall, typically in moves that frame hardship, social mission, vulnerability, or inability to pay, and they often appear alongside counteroffers, concessions, or requests for action. Attackers also use value-laden reasoning in non-trivial ways, especially to frame fairness, proportionality, responsibility, and the alleged legitimacy of the demanded price, and they often appear alongside rejects, counteroffers, proof, or demand anchors. The contrast, then, is not between a moral victim and an amoral attacker. Both sides use value rhetoric, but they use it to support different bargaining moves. Victims use it to justify a lower feasible settlement. Attackers use it to justify the demanded settlement as fair or proportionate. In this corpus, Argument from values works mainly as a framing device that reinforces practical bargaining, rather than as an independent driver of success.

5 Conclusion

Ransomware negotiation is not just coercion with numbers attached. It is an argumentative dialogue in which each side tries to justify, resist, or reshape a deal under pressure. The main takeaway from this study is that practical reasoning is the dominant argumentative pattern: actors talk about means, costs, consequences, and feasible concessions far more than about abstract principle. Value appeals, threats, and evidential claims matter too, but mostly as supporting moves inside bargaining

rather than as independent engines of resolution.

A second takeaway is methodological. Ransomware chats do not respect message boundaries, so a boundary-first, two-stage adjudicated workflow is a better fit than simple turn-by-turn labelling. That workflow makes the data analysable while preserving the structure of short, compressed, and strategically mixed exchanges. In that sense, the study offers not only findings about ransomware negotiation but also a reusable annotation template for other hostile or highly compressed dialogues.

The final takeaway is that the corpus is rich but not closed. Different scheme inventories, segmentation choices, or multilayer designs will likely expose additional regularities, especially around threat, commitment, burden shifting, and procedural manoeuvring. Future work should test whether the same argumentative profile holds across other ransomware families and non-discounted negotiations, and whether finer-grained dialogue modelling can separate bargaining tactic from argumentative force more cleanly.

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A Prompting and Technical Appendix

This appendix reports the operational prompts and the main technical design choices used to construct the final adjudicated corpus. The pipeline was deliberately split into two stages so that the identification of argumentative discourse units (ADUs) could be stabilised before scheme labelling. In the present study, an ADU is treated as a text span with propositional content anchored in the locution itself, or in a transition targeting that locution, and with a discrete argumentative function, such that the proposition stands in a relation of inference, conflict, or rephrase to one or more other propositions. Operationally, stage 1 therefore identifies ADUs at the level of coherent inferential episodes rather than at the level of sentences, messages, or turns.

A.1 Corpus scope and selection

The upstream corpus, in its locally frozen form, contains 25 ransomware groups, 241 chats, and 11,473 messages. The final large annotation run was restricted to the discounted subset selected by the rule `discount_observed=True`. This yielded 46 chats. After adjudication, the resulting dataset contained 598 final argument annotations.

The inclusion rule for the final large run was deliberately broader than the earlier strictly validated success subset. A chat entered the final annotation set if the normalised metadata showed a lower final demanded amount than the initial demanded amount. The result is therefore a corpus of discounted negotiations rather than a corpus of only fully verified payment completions.

A.2 Two-stage annotation design

The final workflow separated two problems that had proved unstable when collapsed into a single pass. Stage 1 identified the boundaries of ADUs. Stage 2 labelled those fixed ADUs for claims, premises, primary Waltonian scheme, optional secondary scheme, optional critical question, dialogue type, and dialogue move. This design made disagreement interpretable: one could distinguish disagreement about where an ADU begins and ends from disagreement about how that ADU should be classified.

The stage-1 output was authoritative for stage 2. Once the stage-1 judge fixed the boundary set, the stage-2 annotators were not permitted to split, merge, or redraw those ADUs.

A.3 Model configuration

The final workflow used two independent annotation models: Azure OpenAI gpt-5-mini and Amazon Bedrock Claude Haiku 4.5 (us.anthropic.claude-haiku-4-5-20251001-v1:0). The judge model in both stages was Amazon Bedrock Claude Sonnet 4.5 (us.anthropic.claude-sonnet-4-5-20251001-v1:0). In three stage-2 cases, Azure content filtering blocked one annotator, so Claude Sonnet 4.5 was also used as a fallback annotator. Even in those cases, the adjudicative logic remained unchanged: two independent annotations followed by judge-based resolution.

A.4 Controlled vocabularies and output constraints

The pipeline relied on fixed inventories in order to improve stability, comparability, and downstream analysis. The phase labels used at stage 1 were corpus-specific operationalisations rather than direct imports from a single published taxonomy.

```
Allowed phase labels:  
contact_identification  
proof_exchange  
bargaining  
payment_arrangement  
post_payment  
breakdown_or_walkaway
```

```
Allowed walton_scheme labels:  
practical_reasoning  
argument_from_negative_consequences  
argument_from_positive_consequences  
argument_from_sign  
argument_from_position_to_know  
argument_from_commitment  
argument_from_values  
no_clear_scheme
```

```
Allowed dialogue_type_primary labels:  
persuasion  
negotiation  
information_seeking  
deliberation
```

```
inquiry
eristic
mixed_or_other
```

Allowed dialogue_move_primary labels:

```
opening
demand_or_anchor
request_information
provide_information
request_proof
provide_proof
offer
counteroffer
concession
accept
reject
threaten
promise_or_commit
request_action
payment_execution
delivery_or_fulfillment
repair_or_followup
close
```

All models were instructed to return one valid JSON object only. The stage-1 judge emitted the authoritative boundary set with preserved span indices and assigned consensus_id values. The stage-2 judge preserved those consensus_id values and emitted the final authoritative label set.

A.5 Stage 1 annotation prompt

```
You are a top-class argumentation scholar and cybersecurity
negotiation analyst.
```

```
You are analyzing one ransomware negotiation chat that has already
been identified as a successful discounted payment case.
```

```
This is stage 1 of a two-stage pipeline.
```

```
The ultimate goal of the project is to map the arguments in the chat
to defensible argumentation schemes.
```

```
At this stage, however, you must focus only on identifying the
correct boundaries between distinct arguments.
```

That means:

- reconstruct the coherent inferential episodes that structure the negotiation
- mark where each argument begins and ends
- keep enough semantic summary to support later scheme labeling
- do not assign Walton schemes yet

Your task is to do two things in order:

1. Read the preprocessed transcript as an argumentation scholar, not as a message-by-message tagger.
2. Return only the core argument boundaries that should later become fixed units for scheme annotation.

Strict rules:

- Do not create a new argument boundary for every message.
- Merge adjacent same-speaker material when it expresses one inferential move.
- Start a new argument when the main claim, target of persuasion, warrant, or negotiation phase changes.
- If timestamps or hard-break markers indicate long discontinuity, treat that as evidence for a new argument unless continuation is explicit.
- Keep the number of argument boundaries as small as possible while still preserving the real argumentative structure.
- Focus only on material argumentative episodes, not every procedural fragment.
- Use between 6 and 12 argument boundaries for the whole chat unless a shorter chat clearly requires fewer.
- Keep every free-text field short.
- 'inferential_core' must be one sentence only.
- 'boundary_rationale' must be one sentence only.
- Return one valid JSON object only.

Boundary defaults you must follow strictly:

- Repeated price revisions from the same speaker remain one argument if the same underlying case is still being advanced.
- A victim's affordability explanation plus adjacent counteroffers usually remain one argument unless the issue shifts into payment execution.
- An attacker's incremental concessions usually remain one argument until the attacker shifts from bargaining into payment execution

- Opening proof-of-possession and credibility display are separate from later price anchoring.
- A new argument starts when the conversation shifts from bargaining to payment execution.
- A new argument starts when the conversation shifts from payment execution to post-payment obligations, deletion evidence, decryptor delivery, or technical aftercare.
- Test-payment and full-payment exchange remain one payment-execution argument unless the test transfer becomes a substantive dispute of its own.

Allowed 'phase' labels:

- 'contact_identification'
- 'proof_exchange'
- 'bargaining'
- 'payment_arrangement'
- 'post_payment'
- 'breakdown_or_walkaway'

Return JSON with this exact structure:

```
{
  "chat_uid": "{{CHAT_UID}}",
  "boundary_annotations": [
    {
      "argument_id": "BA1",
      "speaker_role": "victim",
      "start_turn_index": 0,
      "end_turn_index": 1,
      "start_message_index": 0,
      "end_message_index": 3,
      "uses_timestamp_evidence": false,
      "phase": "bargaining",
      "inferential_core": "short one-sentence summary of the
argument episode",
      "boundary_rationale": "short one-sentence explanation of why
this is one argument",
      "responds_to_argument_ids": [],
      "confidence": 0.86
    }
  ]
}
```

Chat: '{{CHAT_UID}}'

Preprocessed transcript:
{{PREPROCESSED_TRANSCRIPT}}

A.6 Stage 1 judge prompt

You are acting as the adjudicative judge for stage-1 argument-boundary annotation.

You are not annotating the chat from scratch.

You are resolving conflicts between two independent boundary annotations and producing the final stage-1 boundary set for downstream use.

You are a top-class argumentation theorist and cybersecurity negotiation analyst.

This is the boundary stage of a two-stage pipeline.

The later scheme-labeling stage depends on whether the models have identified substantially the same argument units.

Your job is to compare the submitted annotations and resolve disagreement about:

- how many material arguments exist
- where those argument boundaries begin and end
- whether the annotators identified the same inferential episodes
- whether reply structure between arguments is broadly aligned

Important:

- boundary differences that do not change the substantive inferential episode should count as partial agreement, not total disagreement
- small wording differences in 'inferential_core' should count as agreement if the same argumentative episode is being identified
- you should prioritize substantive argumentative identity over surface exactness
- your output must include the final adjudicated set of boundaries that stage 2 must use
- when the two annotations conflict, you must resolve the conflict and choose the best final boundary placement
- the final boundary set is authoritative for the rest of the pipeline

Return one valid JSON object only.

Return JSON with this exact structure:

```
{
  "chat_uid": "{{CHAT_UID}}",
  "judge_model_note": "one short sentence",
  "overall_boundary_agreement_score": 0,
  "overall_boundary_agreement_label": "high",
  "dimension_scores": {
    "argument_count_alignment": 0,
    "span_alignment": 0,
    "inferential_core_alignment": 0,
    "reply_structure_alignment": 0
  },
  "final_boundaries": [
    {
      "consensus_id": "CB1",
      "speaker_role": "victim",
      "start_turn_index": 0,
      "end_turn_index": 1,
      "start_message_index": 0,
      "end_message_index": 3,
      "uses_timestamp_evidence": false,
      "phase": "bargaining",
      "inferential_core": "short summary",
      "adjudication_note": "short explanation of why this boundary
is the chosen final boundary"
    }
  ],
  "material_disagreements": [
    {
      "issue": "short description",
      "severity": "high",
      "explanation": "short explanation"
    }
  ],
  "boundary_adjudication_summary": "one short paragraph"
}
```

Chat: '{{CHAT_UID}}'

Reference transcript:
{{PREPROCESSED_TRANSCRIPT}}

Annotation A:
{{ANNOTATION_A}}

Annotation B:
{{ANNOTATION_B}}

A.7 Stage 2 annotation prompt

You are a top-class argumentation scholar and cybersecurity negotiation analyst.

You are analyzing one ransomware negotiation chat that has already been segmented into fixed final argument boundaries.

This is stage 2 of a two-stage pipeline.

The boundary stage has already been completed.

You must not redraw the argument boundaries.

You must interpret each fixed argument as carefully as possible and transform it into a defensible argumentation-scheme annotation.

Your job is to annotate each final boundary with:

- the main claim
- the explicit premises
- the implicit premises if needed
- the best Walton primary scheme
- optional Walton secondary scheme
- the most relevant critical question if needed
- the primary Walton-and-Krabbe dialogue type
- the primary dialogue move within that dialogue type

Strict rules:

- Do not split or merge the provided consensus boundaries.
- Stay faithful to the supplied boundary spans even if you would personally have segmented differently.
- Keep every text field short.
- 'main_claim' must be one sentence only.
- 'explicit_premises' must contain at most 2 short items.
- 'implicit_premises' must contain at most 1 short item.
- 'walton_scheme_secondary' must contain at most 1 item.
- 'critical_questions' must contain at most 1 short item.
- 'dialogue_type_primary' must use one allowed label only.

- 'dialogue_move_primary' must use one allowed label only.
- Return one valid JSON object only.

Allowed 'walton_scheme' labels:

- 'practical_reasoning'
- 'argument_from_negative_consequences'
- 'argument_from_positive_consequences'
- 'argument_from_sign'
- 'argument_from_position_to_know'
- 'argument_from_commitment'
- 'argument_from_values'
- 'no_clear_scheme'

Allowed 'dialogue_type_primary' labels:

- 'persuasion'
- 'negotiation'
- 'information_seeking'
- 'deliberation'
- 'inquiry'
- 'eristic'
- 'mixed_or_other'

Allowed 'dialogue_move_primary' labels:

- 'opening'
- 'demand_or_anchor'
- 'request_information'
- 'provide_information'
- 'request_proof'
- 'provide_proof'
- 'offer'
- 'counteroffer'
- 'concession'
- 'accept'
- 'reject'
- 'threaten'
- 'promise_or_commit'
- 'request_action'
- 'payment_execution'
- 'delivery_or_fulfillment'
- 'repair_or_followup'
- 'close'

Return JSON with this exact structure:

```
{
  "chat_uid": "{{CHAT_UID}}",
  "scheme_annotations": [
    {
      "consensus_id": "CB1",
      "main_claim": "short plain-language claim",
      "explicit_premises": ["premise 1", "premise 2"],
      "implicit_premises": ["optional premise"],
      "walton_scheme_primary": "argument_from_values",
      "walton_scheme_secondary": ["practical_reasoning"],
      "critical_questions": ["question 1"],
      "dialogue_type_primary": "negotiation",
      "dialogue_move_primary": "counteroffer",
      "confidence": 0.86
    }
  ]
}
```

Chat: ‘{{CHAT_UID}}’

Preprocessed transcript:
{{PREPROCESSED_TRANSCRIPT}}

Final boundaries to annotate:
{{CONSENSUS_BOUNDARIES}}

A.8 Stage 2 judge prompt

You are acting as the adjudicative judge for stage-2 argument-scheme annotation.

You are not redrawing argument boundaries.
The stage-1 judge has already finalized the boundaries.
You are resolving conflicts between two independent stage-2 annotations over the same fixed boundaries.

You are a world-class argumentation theorist, dialogue analyst, and cybersecurity negotiation analyst.

Your job is to compare the submitted annotations and produce the final stage-2 annotation set for each fixed boundary.

You must resolve disagreement about:

- the main claim
- the explicit and implicit premises
- the best Walton primary scheme
- any secondary scheme or critical question
- the primary Walton-and-Krabbe dialogue type
- the primary dialogue move

Important:

- do not split or merge the fixed boundaries
- keep the existing 'consensus_id' values unchanged
- prefer substantive inferential identity over superficial wording differences
- prefer one clear final label over hedging when one option is better supported
- the output of this judge is the final authoritative stage-2 annotation set for downstream analysis

Return one valid JSON object only.

Return JSON with this exact structure:

```
{
  "chat_uid": "{{CHAT_UID}}",
  "judge_model_note": "one short sentence",
  "overall_stage2_agreement_score": 0,
  "overall_stage2_agreement_label": "high",
  "dimension_scores": {
    "claim_premise_alignment": 0,
    "scheme_alignment": 0,
    "dialogue_move_alignment": 0,
    "dialogue_type_alignment": 0
  },
  "final_annotations": [
    {
      "consensus_id": "CB1",
      "main_claim": "short plain-language claim",
      "explicit_premises": ["premise 1", "premise 2"],
      "implicit_premises": ["optional premise"],
      "walton_scheme_primary": "practical_reasoning",
      "walton_scheme_secondary": ["argument_from_values"],
      "critical_questions": ["question 1"],
      "dialogue_type_primary": "negotiation",
      "dialogue_move_primary": "counteroffer",
```

```
    "adjudication_note": "short explanation of why this is the
    final annotation"
  }
],
"material_disagreements": [
  {
    "issue": "short description",
    "severity": "high",
    "explanation": "short explanation"
  }
],
"stage2_adjudication_summary": "one short paragraph"
}
```

Chat: '{{CHAT_UID}}'

Reference transcript:
{{PREPROCESSED_TRANSCRIPT}}

Final stage-1 boundaries:
{{FINAL_BOUNDARIES}}

Annotation A:
{{ANNOTATION_A}}

Annotation B:
{{ANNOTATION_B}}

Table 3: Dialogue moves used in stage-2 annotation

Dialogue move	Operational definition
Opening	The ADU initiates a new interactional sequence.
Demand or anchor	The ADU sets, restates, or defends a demanded amount, condition, or bargaining anchor.
Request information	The ADU asks for factual or procedural information.
Provide information	The ADU supplies factual or procedural information.
Request proof	The ADU asks for proof of possession, access, capability, or performance.
Provide proof	The ADU supplies proof, demonstration, or confirming evidence.
Offer	The ADU proposes a concrete settlement term or transactional option.
Counteroffer	The ADU responds to a prior offer with a revised settlement proposal.
Concession	The ADU yields ground by reducing a demand, softening a position, or accepting part of the other party's terms.
Accept	The ADU accepts a prior offer, condition, or proposed course of action.
Reject	The ADU rejects a prior offer, condition, or proposed course of action.
Threaten	The ADU applies pressure by invoking harm, loss, deadline, or sanction.
Promise or commit	The ADU commits the speaker to a future action, assurance, or undertaking.
Request action	The ADU asks the other party to perform a concrete action.
Payment execution	The ADU performs or coordinates the act of payment itself.
Delivery or fulfilment	The ADU delivers, confirms, or fulfils the expected post-payment good or service.
Repair or follow-up	The ADU addresses troubleshooting, clarification, correction, or further support after an earlier step.
Close	The ADU closes the interaction or marks the end of a sequence.